

THEORETICAL ISSUES OF DEVELOPING TERMINOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN ENGINEERING

Taktasheva Dinara Rinatovna

Associate Professor of “Foreign Languages” department of the Branch of Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University) named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent city

Abstract: This article is devoted to substantiating the significance of terminological competence in professional activity and communication, the need to master terminological competence as the most important indicator of professionalism and a factor in improving the professional communication quality. In addition, the article presents developed structural and functional model of a specialist’s terminological competence as a theoretical basis for studying, as well as demonstrates the indicators of the performance of its components.

Key words: term, terminology, terminological competence, model of terminological competence of a specialist.

Introduction. Recently global changes in all spheres have taken place throughout the world. The labor market is becoming more rigid, forcing to support higher education with additional education aimed at deepening or specializing knowledge and skills.

Under new socio-economic conditions, the development of the education receives a high public profile in the Republic of Uzbekistan, since it is it that will assist the transition to the information society and the formation of priorities for the development of the state. Highly educated youth constitute the main strategic reserve of socio-economic reforms in Uzbekistan. Currently it is impossible to imagine the further development of the society without the youth.

In an effort to acquire the status of a developed state, Uzbekistan supports the development of its entire multi-stage education system, the growth of the intellectual potential of society. It should be noted that according to UNESCO forecasts, the level of national well-being that meets world standards, will be achieved only by those countries whose working-age population will constitute 40-60 percent of people with higher education.

Within this framework mastering a professional language constitutes one of the high-priority objectives of current professional education. This is due to the fact that terminology performs several functions at different stages of the formation of a specialist - at the stage of professional education it acts as a source of knowledge and a tool for mastering professional experience, during the period of professional activity - as a means of professional communication and a theoretical basis for the professional growth of a specialist through its replenishment and updating. Therefore, the terminological competence of the relevant field of knowledge is traditionally an indicator of the quality of assimilation of educational material within the educational process, and its active use in communication among professionals contributes to mutual understanding and cooperation in the experience exchange.

Literature review. Considering the issue of determining the essence and structure of a specialist's terminological competence is justified by a number of objective reasons. The first reason is associated with the intensive development of art, science and technology and emergence of new terms that enable to fix in the language the results of intellectual and creative human activity. As I.N. Churilova notes, the terminological "explosion" resulted in a terminological "barrier" that manifested itself at the beginning of the XXI century and "which became the basic obstacle in solving many problems that arose as a result of the lack of a common understanding and interpretation of terms that function in different spheres of life of both individual peoples and entire countries" (Churilova, 2015). Eliminating this terminological barrier represents paramount importance in intercultural and

professional communication. The second reason is associated with a change in the paradigm of the current education. The transition from a knowledge-based to a competency-based model of education has radically changed the attitude to the significance of terminology in the process of assimilating educational information, and primarily in the disciplines of the humanitarian subject areas. The emphasis is gradually shifting from the elementary reproduction of stable definitions and their most accurate application in educational situations to understanding the terminological diversity of modern humanitarian knowledge. In this regard, there is an increased need not only for differentiation, but also for clarifying the meanings of the terminology used in intellectual, creative, communicative and other types of activity. In this regard, there are being actively carried out terminological studies, which are related to identifying and describing the functions of a term in professional texts of different genres and in various situations of professional communication, defining the features of using terms in speech and computer systems, practical issues of terminography in the design and development of the professional vocabulary. Professional communication traditionally implies communication within the professional sphere between representatives of certain professions (as well as between representatives of related professions).

In recent years, in many countries researches are being carried out on the issues of terminological education of specialists, since scientists and practitioners admit, that terminology, as one of the main features of the scientific style, the informative core of the vocabulary of the language of science and profession, should be reflected at all stages of preparation for professional activities and communication. After all, the sphere of professional activity is served by a special language - the language of professional communication. In the opinion of N.V. Butylov, terminology should formulate the core of the language of professional communication, since it concentrates in itself its main features and properties (Butylov, 2014). That is, scientists pay attention to the importance of knowledge of

terminology in the formation of the linguistic and professional competence of a contemporary specialist.

The description of the functional map of a specific type of professional activity requires the use of special terminology that determines the nature and scope of professional competencies. Currently many studies prove that mastering professional (core subject) competence in a university environment is more successful if this process proceeds in a purposeful, structured manner and in parallel with the study of terminology (V.A. Bukhbinder, T.V. Vasilieva, N.P. Vetlov, E. Yu. Dolmatovskaya, R. K. Minyar-Beloruhev, R. G. Piotrovsky, I. V. Rakhmanov and others). This is justified by the fact that the secrets of any profession underlie the terminology of a specific specialty. It is terminological literacy, contributing to the acquisition of scientific knowledge and practical skills, that makes a specialist more competitive (Yermolaeva, 2016).

Another essential reason is the maintenance of communication in the professional community. Knowledge and accurate use of special terms in the course of direct or indirect communication of professionals ensures the quality of understanding of information, promotes professional consolidation and expands the possibilities for professional experience exchange. From the point of view of L.A. Nesterskaya, “It is the terminology that provides informational understanding of the subjects of the academic sphere: students and teachers, and then the subjects of the professional sphere of communication: managers and subordinates, colleagues, partners, competitors” (Nesterskaya, 2013).

The role of the professional community in enhancing the importance of terminological competence is also ensured by involving its representatives in the expert assessment of the professional education quality. Understanding the specifics of “terminological competence” is impossible without referring to the definition of the “competence” term, which constitutes one of the basic categories in the competence approach.

Analysis and Discussion. As the analysis of scientific and pedagogical literary sources has shown, there is no consensus in the disclosure of the volume and content of the term “competence”.

The need to highlight terminological competence as an independent type is primarily justified by the search for a basis that would enable combining theoretical and practical components of professional activity. Taking into consideration the fact that terminological competence is most significant in professional activity, we will consider it as a component of a broader type of competence - professional. Knowledge of terms, terminological compliances and the ability to use them in speech is the most important component of the professional readiness of a contemporary specialist. Thus, under the terminological competence of a specialist we mean the ability and willingness to competently apply terminology in solving professional problems and in the process of professional communication. There is no consensus among domestic researchers on the issue of the structural organization of competence in general and its types in particular. Therefore, with the existing variety of approaches for understanding the essence of terminological competence, it is significant to perceive and study competence as a polystructural phenomenon. The following provisions have been accepted as the theoretical foundations for constructing a structural-functional model of terminological competence. A term is the main lexical means that fixes a concept in oral and written speech, “a word (or phrase) of a specific subject area, which is the name of a concept and requires a definition” (Danilenko, 1977). It belongs to the logical-conceptual system of a certain branch of scientific knowledge and the lexical system of the general literary language. With the help of terms in a verbal form, the results of the process of cognition of the essence of objects and phenomena of objective reality and the inner life of a person are recorded, as well as the discovery of new scientific knowledge is carried out. They simultaneously reflect the current level of development of the theory and practice of the relevant industry and constitute the basis for their further

development. Such specific functions of the term as heuristic (the discovery of new scientific knowledge) and cognitive (the result of the process of cognizing the essence of objects and phenomena of objective reality and the inner life of a person, verbalization of a special concept) are implemented in this area.

However, the thesaurus description of terminology refers to the methods of representing the subject's knowledge about any subject area. In a thesaurus description, knowledge is fragmented and structured in such a way that it is divided into separate groups of concepts linked by certain relationships. This process relies on a subject-area ontology, which is viewed as a vocabulary of terms specific to a given domain, together with a set of axioms that ensure the interpretation and correct use of these terms. Ontological representation of knowledge is used for semantic integration of information resources, adequate interpretation of the content of text documents and search queries presented in a professional language. In this regard, we believe that a contemporary specialist will freely navigate in the logical-conceptual system of a certain branch of scientific knowledge and the lexical system of the professional language and is ready to develop an individual terminological dictionary as an information basis for understanding the requirements of the corresponding field of professional activity, if he has mobile knowledge in the form of specific terminology.

The psychological basis for the systematization of scientific and practical information about the field of professional activity in the form of concepts that reflect the most important, essential, natural signs of its main objects, phenomena or processes is the conceptual thinking of a specialist. Thus, when developing a structural and functional model of a specialist's terminological competence, as the first component, we consider an informational one, which function is to master the conceptual and terminological apparatus of the subject area of the profession and to develop an individual active professional terminological dictionary, which volume determines the quality of the subject's orientation in theoretical and applied aspects

of mastering the subject area of the profession. We admit differences both in the content and volume of an active vocational vocabulary developed by a specialist at the stage of professional training and self-education, in the course of independent professional activity and during the period of professional development, as well as in the accuracy and completeness of the correct definitions of the corresponding concepts.

A person has the ability to differentiate terms according to areas of knowledge and practice, their definitions are disclosed on the basis of daily experience, communication with other people, information obtained from the media. The level of an active thesaurus assumes knowledge of terminology, which enables to adequately perceive and transmit professionally significant information in written and oral form during communication, to build logical conceptual schemes when solving theoretical and practical problems within the framework of professional duties. Terminology is not only a tool for mastering professionally significant knowledge, skills and abilities, not only a means of communication, but also a means of comprehending and improving professional experience.

Our selection of a practical component in working out the model for the terminological competence development is also justified by the fact that currently linguistics involves the study of language in connection with a person, his consciousness, thinking and activity. In terms of the anthropocentric direction of pedagogical research and linguistics, the study and development of linguistic signs (terms) of specialists is implemented by means of speech-thinking activity. Since the speech activity itself, as a rule, is included in any special (professional, scientific) activity, and the linguistic sign develops in a certain professional sphere (from the stage of its formation to the current state), in so far as the priority in researching the problem of mastering and using terms by specialists belongs to subject-activity approach. This means that for the development of terminological competence, lexical-terminological and professional-language practice is essential at the stage of

study at a university and during the period of independent professional activity and professional communication.

The practical component of terminological competence, in general terms, is the experience of using terms in professional communication. Hence, its core function is communicative and linguistic. However, taking into account the functions implemented by the term in the language of science, it is necessary to specify somewhat the features of the use of scientific terms in professional activities. The communicative function of terms is fully implemented in the process of professional communication. The use of special vocabulary ensures the success of the transfer of professionally significant information, promotes unification of people in a professional community, transfer of knowledge, skills and methods of activity within the professional community, exchange of professional experience, implementation of the function of social control in order to regulate the behavior and activities of employees, etc. Furthermore, the pragmatic function of the term is implemented in professional communication, but, unlike the communicative function, it contributes to the self-expression of the individual, determines efficiency of self-presentation, improves or worsens mutual understanding in joint professional activities.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the research, it is possible to make a conclusion that all the components of the structural and functional model of terminological competence constitute an integral system, therefore they are interconnected, complement and interdependent each other due to their functional purpose (indicative, communicative, creative).

In addition, in reliance upon the research results it can be concluded, that terminological competence has the following characteristics:

1. Diversity of demonstration. This type of competence is implemented in two aspects: an integral characteristic of a person, which is developed in the process of mastering and applying the conceptual and terminological apparatus of a particular

science and (or) the sphere of human activity and a situational characteristic of a person, manifested in the system of working with terms within the boundaries of a certain conceptual and terminological field.

2. Integrativeness. The integrative nature of terminological competence is demonstrated in the fact that it, in one way or another, is present as a component in other competencies.

3. Connection with the terminological potential of the individual.

4. High dependence on education. Terminological competence is developed in two ways - through training and self-education. In the first case, the formation of terminological competence can act as a specially set goal that depends/does not depend on the needs and cognitive interest of students. Herewith knowledge of terminology acts as the basis for mastering specific subject educational material. In the second case, the formation of terminological competence is determined by the motives and cognitive interests of the person himself.

References

1. Butylov N. V. (2014). The role of special terminology in development of professional competence of linguiststranslators. Multiauthored monograph. Edited by O. A. Dronova. Tambov, TROO Biznes-Nauka-Obshchestvo Publishers, 2014, pp. 309–314.

2. Churilova I. N. (2015). Professional terminology as the means of professional communication in training of specialists in performing arts. [Scientific Bulletin of Siberia], 2015, Special issue (15), pp. 223–229.

3. Yermolaeva J. E., Gerasimova I. N. (2014). Development of topical and terminological training vocabulary on the subject of ecology for trainees/ students and course attendees (based on materials of the State Fire Department Academy of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Russian Federation. Proceedings of the

16th International Research-Practice Conference “Theoretical and Methodological Problems of Modern Education”. Moscow, Spetskniga Publishing house, 2014, pp. 106–113.

4. Filippovich Iu. N., Prokhorov A. V. (2002). Semantics of information technology: Experiments with thesaurus and dictionary definitions. Moscow, MGUP Publishing house, 2002, 368 p.

5. Griban O. N. (2012). Subject-matter and structure of informational competence of students of a pedagogical higher education institutions. Conceptual framework of pedagogy and education: collection of studies. Edited by Ye. V. Tkachenko, M. A. Galaguzova. Yekaterinburg, SV96, 2012, issue 7, pp. 336 344.

6. Sharipov Sh. S. (2017). Personality model of modern teacher. Eastern European Scientific Journal - Germany, 2017. Ausgabe 3-2017, ISSN 2199-7977 DOI 10. pp. 93-96.